

Electrochemical behavior of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone

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Manuscript received 20 February 2002, revised 8 July 2002, accepted 16 July 2002

Electrochemical behavior of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone has been studied at dropping mercury and glassy carbon electrodes by employing DC polarography and cyclic voltammetry in Britton-Robinson buffers (pH 2–10). The compound exhibits two polarographic waves in solutions of pH 2–10. In cyclic voltammetric studies, the hydrazone exhibits two cathodic peaks in acid solutions (pH 4.0) and one cathodic peak in alkaline solutions (pH 8.0). The electrode reactions are attributed to the reductive cleavage of =N-N- linkage and the reduction of amide formed in the cleavage.

Isonicotinoylhydrazone derivatives exhibit interesting electrochemical reducible properties under various experimental conditions¹. 5-Bromosalicylaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone (5-Br-SAINH) is one such compound.

This compound possesses interesting features for electrochemical reduction studies, since there are more than one reducible sites in the molecule. Hence we undertook polarographic and cyclic voltammetric studies of the hydrazone in solutions of pH 2–10.

Results and Discussion

The electrochemical characteristics are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Electrochemical reduction in acid solutions :

5-Br-SAINH exhibited two polarographic waves in acid solutions. Typical polarogram is shown in Fig. 1a. Semilogarithmic analysis shows that the wave is irreversible. The limiting current varied linearly with the concentration of the hydrazone and with the square-root of mercury column height. These facts indicate that the wave is diffusion-controlled. The irreversible nature of the wave/peak is established from the shift of $E_{1/2}/E_p$ towards negative potential with increase in concentration of depolarizer and log plot analysis². The absence of anodic peak also lends support to the irreversible nature of the waves and peaks. The half-wave potential shifted towards more negative values with increase in pH. This clearly shows the participation of proton in the reduction process.

Table 1. Polarographic half-wave potentials and wave heights of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone in Britton-Robinson buffers (pH 2–10)

[5-Br-SAINH] = 4×10^{-4} M, medium = 20% aq. DMF (v/v)

pH	I wave		II wave	
	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs SCE)	Wave height cm	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs SCE)	Wave height cm
2	0.72	3.3	0.85	5.2
3	0.91	3.1	1.20	4.0
4	1.05	3.2	1.23	3.7
5	1.08	2.2	1.26	3.4
6	1.18	3.3	1.32	2.5
7	1.20	3.3	1.34	2.4
8	1.22	2.2	1.38	2.4
9	1.24	2.7	1.44	1.8
10	1.28	2.8	1.49	1.8

Table 2. Characteristics of cyclic voltammograms of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone

[5-Br-SAINH] = 4×10^{-4} M, medium = 20% aq. DMF (v/v)

Sweep rate $V s^{-1}$	$-E_{PC I}$	$-E_{PC II}$	$i_{PC I}$	$i_{PC II}$
	V	V	μA	μA
		pH 4.0		
0.050	0.86	1.27	3.6	3.6
0.100	0.89	1.35	6.6	4.8
		pH 8.0		
0.050	1.10	-	2.6	-
0.100	1.15	-	2.6	-

The cyclic voltammogram of the compound shows two cathodic peaks in acid solutions in the forward scan. Typical voltammogram is shown in Fig. 1b. In reverse scan, no

peak was observed. This suggests irreversible nature of the electrode process. This is also confirmed by the negative shift in the peak potentials with increasing sweep rates.

In cyclic voltammetry two cathodic peaks were obtained in acid solutions. From the position of the peaks on the potential axis, the first peak is attributed to the two-electron

The total number of electrons involved in the polarographic reduction process are established as two and four respectively for the first and second waves. The first wave is ascribed to the reductive cleavage of =N–N– linkage involving two electrons. The second wave is attributed to the reduction of the amide to alcohol on the basis of the position of the wave on the potential axis and on the basis of the product analysis.

tron reductive cleavage of =N–N– bond. The second peak is ascribed to the reduction of amide to alcohol.

Electrochemical reduction in alkaline solutions:

5-Br-SAINH exhibited two polarographic waves in alkaline solutions. The effect of mercury column height and concentration of the hydrazone on the wave height suggests that the waves are diffusion-controlled. The waves are found to be irreversible by the semilogarithmic analysis.

The cyclic voltammogram of the hydrazone exhibited only one cathodic peak in the forward scan. In the reverse scan, no peak was observed. This fact indicates the irreversible nature of the electrode process. This is also confirmed by the negative shift in the peak potentials with increasing sweep rates. The first wave is assigned to the reductive cleavage of =N–N– linkage in the compound. Similar wave was reported for isonicotinoylhydrazide³. The second wave is due to the reduction of the amide to alcohol. It is already reported⁴ that amides undergo reduction to the corresponding alcohols.

The observations made in polarographic studies are in agreement with those made in cyclic voltammetric studies, and the half-wave potentials agree well with the peak potentials. A single peak in CV in the alkaline medium indicates that both the reductions may be occurring in single step (corresponding to peak I and peak II in acid medium).

Experimental

5-Br-SAINH was prepared by refluxing equimolar mixture of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and isonicotinoylhydrazide for 2 h using the reported procedure⁵. The yellow coloured product was purified by crystallization from hot aqueous ethanol in the presence of norit, m.p. 253–255°. It was characterized by elemental analysis, IR and NMR spectral studies.

Fig. 1. (a) Typical polarogram of 5-Br-SAINH at pH 4.0 (initial voltage, -0.9 V). (b) Typical cyclic voltammogram of 5-Br-SAINH at pH 4.0 (initial voltage, -0.2 V; sweep rate, 100 mV/s).

Note

Current-voltage curves were recorded in Britton-Robinson buffers (pH 2–10) with an Elico CL-357 polarograph. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in solutions of pHs 4.0 and 8.0 with a Bio-Analytical Systems CV-27 controller and conventional three electrode, Ag/AgCl reference electrode, glassy carbon working electrode and platinum counter electrode. Nitrogen was used as a purge gas.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank U G C , New Delhi, for financial support.

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